

The Perspectives of Parents/Caregivers on HIV Disclosure for Adolescents in Bamenda Health District in the North West Region of Cameroon.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The number of children born to HIV positive women is on the rise, however, most of these adolescents are taking medications for HIV without knowing that they have HIV. Parents are the heads of the basic unit of the society (family). Generally, these parents /caregivers find it difficult to initiate disclosure for their children as they do not know the best or right time to initiate it, for fear that the children are not yet matured enough to handle the issues of HIV disclosure.

Objective: To analyze parents' perspectives on the disclosure of HIV status to adolescents that are on antiretroviral therapy in the Bamenda 1 Health District. **Methods:** this study was a cross-sectional study carried out from September 2023 to December 2023 in the Bamenda 1 Health District. The target population was made up of 100 parents/caregivers of adolescents on ART in 6 different sampled health areas. Data was collected with the use of questionnaires. It was analyzed using SPSS. **Results:** Even though the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines says that disclosure should be done at 12 years, most parents/ caregivers prefer to disclose at later ages between 15 to 21 years. Some of the factors that delay disclosure are; fear of the reactions of the children after disclosure, lack of skills and knowledge on how go about it and also the belief that the child is not mature enough to handle the information on disclosure. **Conclusion:** parents /caregivers know that it is good to tell the child about his or hers condition but fear of the unknown holds them back. There is therefore a need for the health workers to support these parents/caregivers even as to be able to achieve timely disclosure.

Key words: parents/caregivers, perspectives, disclosure, WHO, fear, Bamenda 1 Health District

INTRODUCTION

In Cameroon, research on HIV has targeted antiretroviral therapy adherence (ART) adherence and little has been done on disclosure in Cameroon for now (1-4). Little or no published research has been done on parents/caregivers perspectives on HIV status disclosure for adolescents who are on antiretroviral therapy. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends full disclosure of HIV positive status to adolescents who acquire HIV prenatally by the age of 12 years (5). Making HIV infected children aware of the HIV status is an issue of great concern for public health, partly because of the many proven benefits it brings for mental health, psychosocial development, caregiver wellbeing, treatment adherence and future planning (6). Caregivers/parents consider 12 years as being too young for disclosure (7). Data from research shows that the parents usually consider that the child is too young for disclosure. These parents have often expressed their lack of knowledge and skills on how to do the disclosure. This has led to low rates of disclosure and an increase in the spread of the disease by the adolescents (8). This delay in timely disclosure by the parents/caregivers has also led to the abandonment of treatment by these adolescents since they do not know why they are taking medications on a daily basis (9). In most of our African communities, it is a taboo to talk about sex to a child, this also delays disclosure. Despite the benefits of disclosure to adolescents, Majority of parents/caregivers delay disclosure and prefer that it should be done after 12 years which is not in line with guidelines of WHO (10 to 14).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A qualitative study was carried out in 6 health facilities within the Bamenda 1 health District, from the September 2023 to December 2023. This survey targeted caregivers/parents that attended clinic in the different sampled HIV treatment Centers. Questionnaires were used to collect data in order to assess the perspectives of parents/caregivers on HIV status disclosure for adolescents. A purposive random sampling was done to choose the major HIV treatment centers in Bamenda 1 health district. An authorization was gotten from the administrators of the different HIV treatment centers. On the day of data collection, a volunteer health worker within the HIV treatment unit accepted to screen the parents that were eligible for the survey and then we were given a room where we sat inside with the parents/caregivers and administered the questionnaires. Those eligible were the parents/caregivers that had adolescents with already disclosed HIV status that were on antiretroviral therapy (ART). This work was carried out in the Bamenda 1 health district of the

North West Region of Cameroon. Bamenda 1 health district is made up of 10 health areas, namely; Atuakom , Ntambag, Mendankwe, Mbachongwa, Alamandom, Mankon, Ntankah, Mulang, Alamandom, and Azire. It share borders with the following health districts; to the East it shares borders with Bamenda 3 and Tubah health districts, to the South with Santa and Bali health districts, to the west it shares borders with Mbengwi health district and to the North with Bafut health district. It was carried out in some sampled treatment centers namely, Bamenda Regional Hospital, Azire integrated health Center, Atuakom Integrated Health Center, Saint Mary Soledad Alakuma and the peoples clinic Atuakum. Amongst these HIV treatment was one of the biggest HIV treatment Centers within the Bamenda 1 Health district of the North West Region of Cameroon which is the Bamenda Regional Hospital. Parents /caregivers also have access to a support group, the study population was comprised of Parents/care givers of adolescents with disclosed status in Bamenda health district. These are parents/caregivers of adolescents that have been disclosed to in the sampled health facilities within the Bamenda 1 health district. The inclusion criteria was Parents/caregivers of adolescents that have been disclosed to in the sampled health facilities within the Bamenda 1 health district, who accepted to take part in the study. The exclusion criteria was Parents/caregivers of adolescents that have been disclosed to in the sampled health facilities within the Bamenda 1 health district, who did not accept to take part in the study. For sample size calculation, we used the Yamane's formula .

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where

n= sample size

N= population size

e= margin error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{131}{1 + 131(0.05)^2}$$

$$(0.05)^2 = 0.0025$$

$$1 + 131(0.0025) = 1.3275$$

$$n = \frac{131}{1.3275} = 98.68 = 99 \text{ which was rounded up to } 100, \text{ so our sample size was } 120$$

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For the sampling procedure, both the probability and non-probability methods of sampling were involved. We started with a purposive sampling method, which is a non-probability method of sampling, wherein, the most prominent and biggest HIV treatment Center within the Bamenda Health district was identified and selected. This was the Bamenda Regional Hospital. This was followed by a simple random sampling method which is a probability method of sampling, wherein the names of all the 10 health areas within the Bamenda health district were attributed arbitrary numbers. The numbers were then written down on pieces of papers and folded in such a way that they were not visible. Then a child was asked to pick 4 numbers out of the lot. These 4 numbers corresponded to four health areas within the Bamenda health district. Namely; Azire, Ntambag, Atuakom, and Mankon health areas respectively. Then a purposive sampling was done to identify the most prominent HIV treatment Centers within the sampled health areas. The following HIV treatment centers were identified namely, St Blaise Clinic, Foundation Clinic Atuakom, Saint Mary Soledad Clinic, Azire integrated health Center and Atuakom Integrated Health Center. These were added to the most prominent and biggest HIV treatment Center within the Bamenda Health district which had earlier been identified using the purposive sampling technique at the very beginning, this gave us 6 HIV treatment Centers within the Bamenda health district. In order for us to access the data in the different HIV treatment Centers, we applied for authorization to carry out the data, and waited for it to be granted. The administrators of the different sampled HIV treatment Centers led us to the HIV treatment units and introduced us to the personnel working there. We used questionnaires to collect data from parent/care givers. The parents/ care givers were given to us by the health care workers. The questionnaires were self-administered in an office within the HIV treatment center to provide for privacy and give room for the participants to feel free and give us correct information. . The questionnaires comprised of both open and close ended questions. Data was analyzed also used SPSS. We got ethical clearance from the University of Bamenda, authorization from the Regional Delegation of Public Health and then authorization from the different sampled health facilities in Bamenda 1.

RESULTS

Parents/caregivers perspectives on the disclosure of the HIV seropositive status of adolescents

Socio-demographic Information

The number of parents/caregivers interview was 120. Majority of them were business persons (58.0), followed by civil servants (30.0%). Majority of the participants were parents of the adolescent (60.0%), followed by others like their aunts (35.0%). In terms of religion, the highest numbers of caregivers were Catholic (38.0%), seconded by Presbyterian Christians (35.0%).

Table i: Socio-demographic Information

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Primary profession or occupation		
Business man	69	57.5
Civil servant	36	30.0
Farmer	12	10.0
Reverend sister	3	2.5
Your relationship with this adolescent		
Mother	60	50.0
Grandmother	6	5.0
Father	12	10.0
Others like Aunties	42	35.0
Religion		
Catholic	43	36.0
Presbyterian	40	33.0
Muslim	3	3.0
Baptist	10	8.0
Pentecostal	24	20.0

Perspectives of parents / caregivers on the preferred age for disclosure and readiness of the child

Majority of parents/caregivers reported that disclosure is a process (82.5%). some of them also reported that full disclosure should be done at the age of 15 years (45%), while a few reported 16-19 years (10.0%). For the different ages reported for full disclosure, one main reason was given for the chosen age or age ranges. The reason was that at such age, the child is matured enough to better understand and is ready for the disclosure information (Table ii).

Table ii: Perspectives of parents / caregivers on the preferred age for disclosure following the child's readiness

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Disclosure		
Disclosure is a process	99	82.5
Disclosure is a one –time event	21	17.5
Preferable age for full disclosure		
On or before 12 years	28	23.0
On or before 14 years	26	22.0
15years	54	45.0
16-19years	12	10.0
Reason why you prefer that full disclosure be done on or before 12years		
To make her know the importance of taking the medications	4	3.0
For better understanding and readiness	15	12,5
It will help them adapt to treatment	9	7.5
So that the child know the importance of the medicine	2	2.0
Reason why you prefer that full disclosure be done on or before 14years		
confidentiality	3	2.5
They can better understand at that age	18	15.0
Child is mature and able to handle the information	12	10.0
Reason why you prefer that full disclosure be done at 15years		
Big and mature to understand and is ready for disclosure	36	300
Mature to handle things	9	7.5
Reason why you prefer that full disclosure be done from 16 to 19years		
Because he can reason and understanding better and is ready for disclosure at this age	12	10.0

Perspectives of parent/caregiver on the preferred place for disclosure

The result showed that most of the parents/caregivers prefer that disclosure should take place at the health facility (90.0%), Only few of them reported that the home is more comfortable for such discussions (10.0%) and that mother can explain things better at home than health facility (10.0%). Majority of those who prefer disclosure to be done at the health facility reported that the healthcare personnel are well trained to better counsel the child (83.0%). According to the participants, caregiver/parent, adolescent, health care provider should all be present during disclosure (100%)

Table iii: Perspectives of parents / caregivers on the preferred place for disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Preferable place for full disclosure be done		
At Home	12	10.0
At the health facility	108	90.0
Reasons why you prefer that it should be done at home		
Mother can explain things better to the child	6	5.0
Comfortable zone	3	2.5
Convenient	3	2.5
Reasons why you prefer that it should be done in the health facility		
Healthcare provider are well trained and more skilled	100	83.0
Better counseling	90	75.0
Calm environment	50	42.0
Child will know why and how to handle the situation	6	5.0
Confidential environment	40	33.0
Persons to be present during the disclosure		
Caregiver/parent, adolescent, health care provider	120	100.0

Perspectives of parents / caregivers on the best person to do the disclosure

It was reported that the healthcare provider is the best person to do the disclosure (67.5%).

Reasons being that health workers have the adequate knowledge and skills on disclosure

(62.0%) and they can better manage the reactions to the adolescents following disclosure (50.0%). Most of them reported disappointment on the side of the child after disclosure (60%).

Table iv: Perspectives of parents / caregivers on the best person to do the disclosure

Variable(n=120)	frequency	percentage
The best person to do the disclosure		
Health care provider	81	67.5
Caregiver/parent	39	32.5
Reason why disclosure should be done by a health care provider		
They have the knowledge and skills on disclosure	74	62.0
they can manage the reactions of the adolescents	60	50.0
Rawson why disclosure should be done by the parents		
We know the child better	39	32.5
Reaction of the child after disclosure		
Not Calm	72	60.0
Calm	48	40.0
If the child was not calm, can you describe what happened immediately after disclosure		
The child was distress, confused and lack self esteem	11	9.0
Child cried for some days	70	58.0
Child was very disappointed	50	42.0

Perspectives of parents/caregiver on the care of the child after disclosure and the facilitators of disclosure

40% of them reported an increase in their love and care for the child after disclosure following the child’s disappointment and depression. Some facilitators of disclosure that were identified included the following; Knowledge of availability of ART(75.0%) and the View of disclosure as

the right of the adolescent (80.0%), Persistent inquiries by HIV positive adolescents(85.0%) and Presence of chronic illness in the adolescent (50.0%).

Table v: Perspectives of parents / caregivers on care of the child after disclosure and the facilitators of disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Handling of the child after disclosure		
Close observation	36	30.0
Extra love and care	48	40.0
Make her know that she is not alone	9	7.5
Ready to cooperate	24	20.0
Treatment started	3	2.5
Some facilitators of disclosure		
Knowledge of availability of ART and the view of disclosure as the right of the adolescent	90	75.0
Persistent inquiries by HIV positive adolescents and the presence of chronic illness in the adolescent	96	80.0
questions from the child	102	85.0
refusal of the child to take medicine again	60	50.0
	102	85.0
	12	10.0

Perspectives of care givers/parents on the support given to them by health care providers and the barriers of disclosure

40.0% of them reported that the health care providers usually provide support to them for the disclosure preparation such as giving finances to help them to attend disclosure sessions.28.0% of them said that the health care providers teach them how to communicate on disclosure with their children and 20.0% said that they carry out disclosure counseling with them. Few parents (27.5%)do take their medication along with the child for various reasons such as; to make the child know that the medication is not bad, to encourage the child to adhere to his or her treatment and to encourage the child to know that he/she is not alone. Majority of the parents/caregivers (72.5%) do not take medication along with their children for various reasons such as; the caregiver being free and not on HIV treatment, their work does not permit them to take the medication with the child. (Table VI). Some barriers of disclosure that were identified were; the adolescent is considered to be too young for disclosure and may not be able to keep the HIV status as a secret (93.0%), fear of the reaction of the child after disclosure (97.5%), cultural norms that prohibits the

discussion of sexual issues with children (94.0%), the lack of knowledge and skill for disclosure (28.0%) and fear and stigma experiences (81.0%).

Table VI: Perspectives of parents / caregivers on disclosure support

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Type of support usually provided by health care providers to caregivers/parents in preparation for disclosure		
They give us material for disclosure	15	12.0
They give us finances to help us to attend disclosure sessions	48	40.0
They carry out disclosure counseling with us	24	20.0
They teach us how to communicate on disclosure with our children	33	28.0
Some of the barriers of disclosure		
The child is considered too young for disclosure, and will not be able to keep the HIV status as a secret	112	93.0
A lack of readiness to discuss sex, with the child	113	94.1
Fear and stigma experiences	98	81.0
Lack of skill and knowledge on how to do disclosure	86	72.0
Cultural norms that prohibit the discussion of sexual issues with children	113	94.0
Fear of the reaction of the child after disclosure	117	97.5
Protection of the child from HIV related stigma and discrimination	98	81.6
You usually take your medications together with your child		
I do	33	27.5
I do no	87	72.5
If you do, reasons		
make her know that the medication is not bad	27	22.5
To encourage her to adhere to her treatment	25	20.5
To encourage the child to know that he is not alone	23	19.1
To teach the child the importance of taking the medication	18	15.0
If you do not , reasons		
I am not on HIV treatment	75	62.5
My work does not permit me to be at home all the time	32	26.6

DISCUSSION

Discussion on the perspectives of parents/ caregivers on disclosure

The number of parents/caregivers interviewed were 120. Most of them were business persons (58.8%), followed by civil servants (30.0%). Some of the participants were parents of the adolescent (60.0%), followed by others like their aunts (35.1%). In terms of religion, some of the caregivers were Catholics (35.7%) and Presbyterian Christians (36.0%). Majority of the parents reported that disclosure is a process, from partial disclosure to full disclosure (82.5%). This concurs with the findings from a systematic review carried out in SSA, which reported that disclosure was defined by mention of “HIV or AIDS” when explaining the illness to infected children and adolescents implying full disclosure. Otherwise partial disclosure is the case (15 to 20). Some of the parents reported that disclosure should be done at the age of 15years (45.0%) instead of 12years as recommended by the WHO. It concurs with some studies which reported 15 years as the best age for disclosure to the adolescents (21, 22).

Majority of the parents /caregivers preferred that disclosure should be done in a health facility(90.0%).this concurs with other studies which reported that for caregivers who preferred that their care providers be involved in the disclosure process, the health facility was the natural setting where this occurred(23,24 and 25). Most of the parents/caregivers (67.5%) preferred disclosure to be done by health care providers. this concurs with another study which reported preference for health care providers to disclose rather than caregivers (26 and 27). Also Most of the parents/caregivers did not have the necessary support needed for disclosure from health care providers as only(12.5%) of them were given the necessary materials needed for disclosure, which concurs with other findings from other research which reported that parents did not have enough materials for disclosure (28). Some of them reported an increase in their love and care for the child after disclosure following the child’s disappointment and depression (40.0%).

Some facilitators of disclosure that were identified included the following; Knowledge of availability of ART(75.0%),View of disclosure as the right of the adolescent (80.0%),Persistent inquiries by HIV positive adolescents (85.0%) and Presence of chronic illness in the adolescent (50.0%). This concurs with the findings from another study which reported that the benefits of disclosure serves as a facilitator for disclosure, also that, it is the right of the child to know and

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that it is the responsibility of the caregiver to inform the child of his disease condition (29). It was reported that parents /care givers are motivated to disclose, when the child keeps asking many questions, like why am I taking medicine when I am not sick(85%). Also because the child refused to take his medications again (10%). Also the availability of ART 75.0%) and also because the child was constantly sick (50%) which is similar with the results of this other work (29).

. Some of the barriers of disclosure reported were; the fact that the parents considered the children to be too young for disclosure and will not be able to keep the HIV status as a secret (93.0%), the fear of the reaction of the child after disclosure (97.0%) This concurs with other findings where 90% of the participants said that the child was not old enough to understand. And 95% of them reported the fear of how the child will react to the news of the diagnosis (30, 31). We also analyzed that 94% of the participants reported a lack of readiness to discuss sex, if the child ask how he got infected which is in line with another study which reported that 90% of the parents reported also on a lack of readiness to discuss sex issues with the child (32). Furthermore, 81% of the parents /caregivers strived to protect the child from HIV related stigma and discrimination by delaying disclosure, which concurs with other studies that reported 80% of the parents delayed disclosure in order to protect the child from stigma and discrimination (33). In addition, 72% of the parents/caregivers did not know what and how to tell the child, which concurs with another study which reported that 70% of the parents did not know what to do (34). it was also observed that, out of the 60 (50.0%) mothers, only 33 (27.5%) took their medications the same time with the infected children, and the rest of them claimed not to have HIV, this being an indication that most of the mothers have not accepted their status. This concurs with other works where it was seen that non-acceptance of HIV status was a barrier to disclosure of HIV status as the disbelief, perceived stigma and fear of negative judgement may force the HIV infected individuals to hide their positive results. Following our research work, majority of the children were not calm after disclosure (60.0%), however, some of the children were calm(40.0%).those that were not calm manifested the following behaviors; sadness, crying for some days, frustration, anger, aggressiveness, and revolt were the common reactions of the children following disclosure. This concurs with other works that reported that, the most common immediate reactions of HIV status disclosure were anger, aggressiveness, revolt, sadness, frustration, and cries (35, 36).

Limitations

The sensitive nature of the study made the work to be very difficult as it was difficult to identify the participants to work with

5.4 CONCLUSION

Disclosure is to progressively cause the adolescent to understand his or her HIV status. It is a process. It starts with partial disclosure and gradually progresses to full disclosure. In this study, most of the mothers to these adolescents had not actually accepted their HIV status. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), disclosure to the adolescents should be done at 12years, but majority of the parents preferred to disclose to the adolescents at a later age. According to the parents, the child was not ready for disclosure at 12years. Majority of the Parents preferred that health care providers do the disclosure at a health facility and at 15years and above. Some of the barriers of disclosure were the lack of knowledge and skill of disclosure by the parents, the fear of how the child will react to the news of the diagnosis, the child was considered too young for disclosure and will not be able to keep the HIV status as a secret, a lack of readiness to discuss sex if the child ask how he got infected , parents /caregivers strived to protect the child from HIV related stigma and discrimination by delaying disclosure, the facilitators of disclosure included the following; it was the right of the child to know his condition, it was their responsibility to tell the child, the benefits of disclosure, child asking many questions, like why am I taking medicine when I am not sick, at times, the child's refusal to take medications, the availability of ART and also because the child was constantly sick. There is the need to empower these parents on disclosure in order to enhance timely disclosure.

Perspectives for future studies

Perspectives of mothers on the issue of non-acceptance of HIV status

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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